

Milestone n. 16 (Report)

Handbook of protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions

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Handbook of protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions

This milestone is associated with D7.4. Protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions were collected both in the MOOC, in the Session I and II available at the link: <https://sites.google.com/view/prosmallagrimedproject/home-page/crop-management> and <https://sites.google.com/view/prosmallagrimedproject/home-page/soil-management>, and in the handbook of protocols and methodology of good agricultural practices in arid and semiarid conditions – this handbook will collect all the protocols was prepared by Sonia Labidi leader of the WP3 in ProSmallAgriMed project.